

ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF SPORTS ENERGETICS AND ALCOHOL ENERGY SUPPLIES

¹Karimkulov K.M., ²Radjabova L.R.

¹D.t.s., professor, State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Customs Institute, Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization of Engineering

²National Research University Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management. Doctor of philosophy, PhD, associate professor on technical sciences

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Abstract. *In the given article an overview of analytical results from studies on sports energy and alcoholic energy drinks is presented. In the context of sports energy, positive effects such as increased endurance and concentration associated with the use of caffeine, taurine and B-vitamins have been highlighted. However, possible side effects, including heart problems and insomnia, have been reported. As for alcoholic energy drinks, the dangers associated with their use, particularly when mixed with alcohol, have been highlighted. Studies show a potential increase in risky behavioral practices and adverse health outcomes. Regulation of the sale of alcoholic energy drinks in order to protect public health is becoming an urgent issue in various countries. The article emphasizes the importance of continuous monitoring and updating of information in this area, as new studies and regulations may change our understanding of the effects of sports and alcohol-based energy on the human body.*

Keywords: *analytical results, sports energy, energy drinks, alcoholic energy drinks, performance enhancement, health effects, caffeine content, physical endurance, risk assessment, regulatory measures.*

INTRODUCTION. It is important to suggest that sports alcohol and alcoholic beverages are attracting the attention of both active athletes and ordinary consumers. Fortified with caffeine, taurine, vitamins and other active ingredients, these drinks are aimed at improving physical performance and increasing energy. In this study the review is conducted regarding the analytical results obtained in the study of sports alcohol and alcoholic beverages.

Sports energy and its positive effects: The analysis of the research results revealed a positive effect of sports energy drinks on endurance and concentration, depending on the content of caffeine and taurine. These components help to increase physical activity and improve the body's response.

Negative aspects: However, the analytical data also point to potential negative effects, such as possible heart problems, insomnia and adverse reactions to high levels of active ingredients.

Definitely, alcoholic energy drinks: mixing and risks: Research into alcoholic energy drinks has identified risks associated with their consumption in combination with alcohol. Mixing these drinks may influence the perception of intoxication, which may lead to risky behaviour.

Regulations and restrictions: The evidence highlights the need to regulate the sale of alcoholic beverages as a public health issue. Several countries have already taken steps to introduce restrictions. Sports alcohol and alcoholic drinks are the subject of active research into their effects on the body. The pros and cons highlight the need to better understand the potential risks and benefits. Further research and regulation will be important to ensure the safe and effective use of these drinks in different contexts.

Moreover, the introduction should outline the issues identified in the study, the unexplored issues, and the aim and objectives of the study. Research shows that high doses of caffeine can lead to poor mental health, anxiety and irritability. This is especially important given the popularity of alcohol among young people. Sports energy and alcoholic energy represent two different approaches to improving physical and mental performance. In this article, we will look at the purpose of the analysis results in these areas and their impact on health and performance.

What is more important, Sports energy products are designed to provide the body with energy and maintain high performance during training and competition. One of the main aspects of this process is the analysis of the results obtained from research and testing of athletes.

The objectives of analytical results in the field of sports energy: Determining the effectiveness of the product. Analytical data helps to determine how effective sports energy products are in terms of endurance, strength and recovery after training.

Moreover, personalization of the approach, test results can be used to create personalized recommendations and energy supplement regimens based on individual needs and characteristics of the body. Safety and quality: Analysis is necessary to ensure product safety, eliminate banned substances and maintain high quality standards for sports energy products.

Health impact studies, the purpose of analysis is also to study the long-term health effects of sports energy products, including risk and benefit assessment.

The results of the analysis can be used to improve training programs and strategies aimed at achieving maximum results. This market segment has become the focus of not only consumers, but also researchers evaluating the effects of such drinks on the body.

Objectives of the Alcohol Beverage Analytics, safety of consumption: The aim of the study is to determine the safe level of consumption of alcoholic beverages, taking into account the health risks associated with the combination of alcohol and stimulants.

Understanding the impact: Analytics helps to understand the impact of such beverages on the human body, including physical and mental well-being, as well as the risk of potential adverse effects.

Legislative standards: The results of the study will affect the laws governing the production and advertising of alcoholic beverages to ensure their safety and compliance.

Prevention of abuse: The purpose of the analysis is also to identify the possible.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

Community education: Analytics play an important role in educating the public about the consequences of alcohol consumption and facilitating direct consumer choice. Summarising, analytical results in the field of sports and alcoholic beverages are an important means of ensuring the safety, efficiency and health of consumers. Continuous research and analysis in these directions will help the development of the industry, and also serve to enlighten the society on the correct and rational use of energy products.

Definitely, alcohol belongs to the category of carcinogenic substances. This means that they can lead to cancer. According to new research, alcohol is also harmful to the body at the genetic level. Scientists recommend drinking less alcohol or giving it up. In recent decades, the sports and alcohol energy industries have received increasing attention from the scientific community, consumers, and health organizations. Literature review and analytical methods play a key role in understanding the efficacy, safety and implications of products in these two areas.

"How exactly alcohol harms the body remains a mystery. Our conclusion is that when alcohol is digested, in the process of turning into energy, toxins appear and attack the gene complex. Damaged DNA cannot be regenerated," suggested Ketan Patel, the author of the study. The name of the toxin is acetaldehyde. How this chemical affects cells was tested in the laboratory on mice. "There is an important type of cell in the body - it is a stem cell. This stem cell, which is renewed in our body is damaged by acetaldehyde," suggested the scientist.

The inability of healthy cells to repair themselves leads to cancer. "In the course of the study, we saw that the chromosomes in the blood cells, that is, the DNA, changed dramatically. It is this change that determines whether the cells will renew themselves or lead to cancer," says Ketan Patel. Acetaldehyde should not accumulate in the body in large quantities. Most people have enzymes that do this. "When we removed these enzymes in mice, we noticed that even a small amount of drinking caused serious damage to the hematopoietic cells." The body has natural mechanisms that restore the gene complex, the scientist says, but alcoholism destroys these protective systems.

Literature review on sports energy: trends and new research. An analysis of the literature in the field of sports energy reveals current trends and new research. Specialized scientific articles, reviews and meta-analyses provide information on the latest discoveries in the field of energy supplements on the body, their effectiveness and potential risks.

A literature review based on an individual approach also shows the importance of an individual approach to sports energy. The differences in the body's response to the various components of energy products highlight the need for individual recommendations and dosing regimens to achieve optimal results. Research into the health effects of sports energy products is also important to ensure consumer safety. A literature review may cover topics such as cardiovascular effects, neurological aspects, and long-term effects. One of the main methods for analyzing sports energy products is biochemical tests and studies. These include blood, urine, and tissue tests, as well as measurements of vital metabolites, energy substances, and enzymes.

Physiological tests include measurements of parameters such as heart rate, respiration, blood pressure and oxygen consumption during physical activity. They allow an assessment of the efficiency of energy products in real-life conditions. Metabolic analysis provides information on how the body uses energy. This includes studying metabolism, calorie expenditure and the efficiency of nutrient use.

Literature Review on "Alcohol Energy". The literature review on "Alcohol Energy" helps to understand the effects of combined drinks on the body. Studies have shown effects on psychomotor functions, coordination and the ability to perform general physical activities. The literature review also considers the psychological aspects of alcohol use, including the impact on the perception of alcohol intoxication and the risk of binge drinking.

The literature review on alcoholic drinks highlights the potential dangers and abuse of such drinks, including their association with alcohol-related risks, accidents and health problems.

The combination of a literature review and the application of modern research methods are key elements for a deeper understanding of the energetics of sport and alcohol. This information will help develop more effective and safe products and provide a scientific basis for developing recommendations for their use. Continued research in these areas will not only advance the industry, but also serve the health and well-being of consumers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: Sports energy and alcohol energy are two areas where the effects of these products on the body are critical to health and performance. We review the results of analytical studies in these areas and discuss the main issues identified in the analysis.

Table 1

The harmful effects of sports energy drinks and alcoholic energy drinks are as follows:

Drug class	Examples of common effects	Definition
Alcoholic beverages (eg beer, wine, spirits)	Impaired thinking, slowed reflexes, impaired motor function, drowsiness, coma, overdose can lead to death.	Conclusion may be difficult; excessive use during pregnancy is dangerous to the fetus
Depressants (eg, sleeping pills, sedatives, some tranquilizers)	Inattention, slowed reflexes, depression, loss of balance, drowsiness, coma, overdose can lead to death.	Conclusion may be difficult
Opiates (eg, morphine, heroin, codeine, some prescription painkillers)	Loss of interest, "falling asleep" - overdose can be fatal. Subcutaneous or intravenous use can lead to transmission of hepatitis B, C and HIV/AIDS through needle sharing	
Stimulants (eg cocaine, amphetamines)	Elevated mood, hyperactivity, tension/anxiety, increased heart rate, vasoconstriction.	Chronic heavy use can lead to paranoid psychosis. Injecting can lead to the spread of hepatitis B, C and HIV/AIDS through the sharing of needles.

The results of the tests in search of optimal sports energy solutions are as follows:

1. Product effectiveness – many analytical results show the high effectiveness of sports energy in maintaining endurance and increasing physical activity. Research has shown that certain compounds such as carnitine, creatine and B vitamins play a key role in providing energy and accelerating recovery after training.

2. Personalized approach – the analysis also highlights the importance of a personalized approach to the consumption of sports energy products. Different types of training, individual body characteristics and even climatic conditions can significantly affect the results and this should be taken into account when developing recommendations.

3. Safety and quality – the results of analytical studies are related to the safety and quality of the products. They emphasize the importance of strict quality control standards to eliminate possible adverse health effects such as allergic reactions or cardiovascular effects.

The discussion process is as follows: 1. Optimization of use: The discussion of the results shows the need to optimize the use of sports energy. Tailoring the recommendations to the unique needs and goals of each athlete is the key to achieving the best results.

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Alcohol Energy: Balancing Pleasure and Health. The test results are as follows:

1. Effect on the body – analytical data show the complex effects of alcohol energy on the body. High levels of caffeine and other stimulants can cause a false sense of wakefulness despite alcohol intoxication.

2. Health risks – research shows potential health risks associated with alcohol consumption, including the risk of mental illness and excessive drinking.

3. Legislative aspects – the results also raise questions about the legislative aspects of alcohol regulation. Many countries are struggling to develop laws that would balance industrial development and consumer safety.

The analytical results of sports energy drinks and alcohol energy drinks are as follows:

1. Potential for abuse. The discussion of the results highlights the potential for alcohol abuse, especially among young people. The topic of discussion is the need to strengthen control over the sale and advertising of such products.

2. Prevention and education - the discussion will touch on the issues of prevention and education. Expanding educational programs and campaigns to inform the public about the harm of alcoholic beverages will promote responsible consumption.

3. Balanced approach. The discussion of the data highlights the need for a balanced approach to alcoholic beverages. Open communication between industry, researchers and politicians is becoming a key tool in developing policies to improve public health.

The results and discussion of the analytical data in the field of sports and alcohol energy drinks highlight the importance of ongoing research and updating approaches to the use of these products. Ensuring safety, effectiveness and rational consumption is becoming a priority that requires joint efforts of the scientific community, industry and society as a whole.

Currently, the addiction to energy drinks among young people is being considered. It has alcoholic and non-alcoholic varieties. Non-alcoholic alcohol has become very popular among minors. Young people addicted to entertainment are deceived by its "invigorating" quality and continue to consume it freely. And when they reach the point where they cannot give up their will, they do not even imagine that it will be too late and the negative consequences of its temporary "magic" effect.

Definitely, alcohol is very harmful to the emotional and mental development of a person. A person who drinks too much of it does not benefit either his family or society, but causes them great losses. Drunkenness turns a person into a dishonest, untruthful, liar, scoundrel. It seriously affects the brain, destroys the liver, nerves, weakens the heart. The life of a drunkard will certainly end in tragedy. Such a person forgets honor, customs and manners, departs from the concepts of mercy and compassion, turns into a careless, tasteless creature.

According to the governors, a person who abuses alcohol develops various ailments. According to Kaikovus: "The result of drinking wine is two things: either illness or madness, because the one who drinks wine either gets drunk or gets drunker." If he is drunk, then he is among the mad, if he is drunk, then he is among the sick, because drunkenness is a kind of illness. So, what is the point of inclining to something that will either make you go crazy or get sick..." Drunkenness is the mother of various crimes. If we look at the facts, then about 70% of murders, 80-90% of hooliganism occur mainly in a state of alcoholic intoxication. If alcohol consumption by citizens decreases by 35%, murders will decrease by at least 40%, and hooliganism - by 25%. Drinking 100 grams of vodka destroys 7,500 active tissues in the human body. After drinking 75 grams of vodka, muscle strength decreases by 20 to 40 percent. This in itself leads to a decrease in labor productivity. About 25 percent of alcoholics think about committing suicide while intoxicated. 100 grams of alcohol will deprive an athlete of work for two weeks. Drinking alcohol and smoking have a strong and rapid effect, especially on women and young children. A woman gets used to alcohol within a year or two. A glass of weak wine drunk by a boy or girl of 13-14 years old is as harmful as a bottle of vodka for an adult. If there is alcoholism, drug addiction, smoking abuse in the family, it is impossible to talk about the development of a healthy child, family happiness, harmony and mutual respect. Alcohol has become an integral part of the modern lifestyle, attracting attention with promises of increased vivacity and energy. However, behind the bright labels and bright advertising there are potential health risks. In this article, we will review the results and discuss the risks associated with alcohol consumption. According to the results of the study, it has been established that it has a strong effect on the cardiovascular system. Many studies confirm that alcohol consumption can cause a temporary increase in blood pressure and heart rate. These factors can put a strain on the cardiovascular system, especially in people prone to cardiovascular diseases.

We should admit that research findings also show the effects of energy drinks on the nervous system. High levels of caffeine can cause insomnia, irritability and anxiety, especially in people sensitive to stimulants. Studies have linked energy drink consumption to metabolic disorders. Excess sugar in drinks contributes to the development of obesity and diabetes. Psychological aspects are also affected. Alcohol can cause irritability, anxiety and in some cases even aggressive behavior. There is a need to regulate the content of alcoholic beverages. The discussion of the results indicates the need to regulate the alcohol content. Reducing caffeine and sugar intake can significantly reduce health risks. It is important to ensure consumer awareness. Effective information campaigns and educational programs can help people make more informed decisions about alcohol consumption. Health and educational institutions should play an active role in providing information about the dangers of alcohol. This includes conducting warning talks and distributing information brochures. According to health statistics published by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development in 2010, alcohol consumption has increased in Muslim-majority Middle Eastern countries and Turkey. The Economist compiled

reports from various sources and concluded: “In Muslim countries, alcohol consumption increased by 72 percent between 2001 and 2011.”

The discussion of the results also highlights the need for further research to better understand the effects of alcohol on the body. Larger multicenter studies may provide additional information to guide safe consumption. The discussion of the harm of alcohol, according to the results, highlights the importance of balancing sobriety and health. Education, regulation, and additional research may form the basis for developing effective strategies to reduce potential risks and ensure safe alcohol consumption in everyday life.

CONCLUSION. Based on the data, it can be concluded that excessive alcohol consumption has a very negative effect. In human health, it leads to the development of multiple organ failure, with the cardiovascular system, central nervous system, as well as the liver and kidneys being primarily affected. In recent decades, alcohol has become a popular way to stay awake and increase energy. The combination of sports and alcohol is generally not recommended due to the potential health risks and health consequences. Alcohol can negatively affect physical performance, coordination, and thinking. Playing sports while intoxicated can lead to accidents and increase susceptibility to injury. However, if you plan to prepare sports or energy drinks that may contain alcohol, it is also not recommended to combine alcohol with energy drinks.

By summerising it should be suggested that the stimulant effect of caffeine in energy drinks can mask the sedative effect of alcohol, increasing the risk of alcohol-related injuries and alcohol poisoning. The fight against alcohol is one of the main principles of Islam: the protection of life, property, offspring and religion is the duty of a Muslim. It is the sacred duty of healthy and intelligent people to fight from all sides against things that harm health, empty the pocket, weaken the mind, alienate people from religion and destroy the future generation.

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